

LET'S PROTECT SHEEP FROM BAVICOLOSIS

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Annotation: The article describes the distribution of bovicola ectoparasites found among sheep.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada qo'ylar orasida uchrayotgan bovicola ektoparazitlarining tarqalishi bo'yicha ma'lumotlar bayon etilgan.

Key words: Bovicolosis, lice, fleas, ticks, fleas, linognathosis, ctenocephalidosis, ectoparasite, ectoparasitosis.

Kalit so'zlar: Bovikolyoz, bit, burga, kana, junxo'r, linognatoz, ktenotsefalidoz, riptsefalyoz, ektoparazit, ektoparazitoz.

Relevance of the topic. Due to the climate of our republic, the fact that sheep feed does not require a lot of cost, rapid reproduction and high level of fertility, the nutritional value of meat products, the necessity of wool and leather products for industry, their value, and the high demand for them are different types of sheep. distinguished from domestic animals. Sheep breeding is a convenient and profitable industry for private and subsidiary farms. Because every family living in the village can increase their income by keeping and raising sheep, eating their meat, making various products from their wool and selling it to the market. Various products are made from sheep's wool. Sheep meat is widely used as food. That is why purebred sheep are brought to our republic from European countries.

The purpose of the research is to study the fauna and dynamics of seasonal distribution of ectoparasites parasitizing sheep in private and farms.

Research materials and methods. Modern recommendations and methodological manuals of parasitological, entomological, epizootological, microscopic examination, ecological-faunistic and veterinary parasitology sciences were used in the research.

Research results. 2023 research on the distribution of ectoparasites causing ectoparasitic disease in sheep, 290 sheep at the Chavandoz farm, Nurabad district, Samarkand region, Khudoykulov F.I. 360 sheep in the livestock farm, 130 sheep in the "Jamshid" farm, 131 sheep belonging to U. Boboev, a resident of "Boshkuduq" village, 836 belonging to "Nurobad Karakol Breeding" LLC. in sheep, ectoparasites found by parasitological examination were collected and their morphology was studied, species, genus, and systematics were determined. As a result, *B. ovis*, *Ctenocephalides ovis*, *Linognathidae ovis*, *Rhipicephalus bursa* species of ectoparasites and ectoparasitoses were identified in sheep (Table 1, Figures 1-2).

Ectoparasites and ectoparasitoses detected in sheep

Table 1

Animal species	Found ectoparasite types	The name of ectoparasites	
<i>In sheep</i>	<i>Bovicola ovis</i>	Bovicolosis	entomosis
	<i>Ctenocephalides ovis</i>	Ctenocephalidosis	entomosis
	<i>Linognathidae ovis</i>	Linognathosis	entomosis
	<i>Rhipicephalus bursa</i>	Rhipicephalosis	akarosis

Parasitological examination procedure

Found bovicolas

Among sheep, mainly *Bovicola ovis*, *Ctenocephalides ovis*, *Linognathidae ovis* ectoparasites and ectoparasitic diseases such as bovicolosis, ctenocephalidosis, linognathosis, rhycephalosis, and *Bovicola ovis* ectoparasite as the dominant species were found to be widespread and cause bovicolosis disease in sheep. They are mostly found in farms where the conditions of sanitation and hygiene, feeding and keeping sheep with sufficient nutritious food do not meet the requirements, long-term transportation of sheep, i.e. bringing them from one country to another (migration), were observed to spread through wools, skin raw materials and water (during bathing and drinking) and were observed during all seasons of the year. It was found that high humidity and comfortable temperature in the building, lack of sunlight in the winter months, long sheep wool, poor-quality feeding and dense storage create favorable conditions for the development and rapid spread of *Bovicola ovis*.

Thus, *Bovicola ovis* can be found in the body of sheep in all seasons, but the extent and intensity of the invasion varies according to the season, i.e., the damage is at its maximum in the months from January to April, the minimum in the months from June to September, November- it was observed to be in average condition in December (Table 2).

The degree of infection of sheep with bavicoliosis by month

Table 2

The name of the dominant ectoparasitosis found	Damage by months, %											
	<i>I</i>	<i>II</i>	<i>III</i>	<i>IV</i>	<i>V</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>VII</i>	<i>VIII</i>	<i>IX</i>	<i>X</i>	<i>XI</i>	<i>XII</i>
Bovicolosis	72	85	95	95	75	10	5	4	10	15	20	30

*The damage indicators for these months were summarized and the dynamics of seasonal damage to sheep with *Bovicola ovis* was determined. In this case, it was found that the average of sheep in the spring season is - 95, in the summer months - 5.0, and in the autumn months - 10.5, in the winter months it is -55 percent, and it is epizootic (Table 3).*

Seasonal dynamics of bavicolosis in sheep

Table 3

The name of the found ectoparasites	Damage by seasons, %			
	<i>Winter</i>	<i>Spring</i>	<i>summer</i>	<i>Autumn</i>
Bovicolosis	55,0	95,0	5,0	10,5

Summary.

1. Among a total of 1,747 head of sheep examined in Samarkand region, in the conditions of sheep farming and private farms of the population, the occurrence of ectoparasitic diseases such as *Bovicola ovis*, *Linognathidae ovis*, *Ctenocephalides ovis*, *Rhipicephalus bursa* species and bovicolliosis, of which the causative agent of bovicolliosis is *Bovicola ovis* was found to be widely distributed as the main dominant species in the body of sheep.

2. Bovicolosis occurs in sheep in all seasons. However, the incidence varies according to the season. In January-February-March-April-May, damage is maximum, June-July-August-September-October is minimum, and November-December is average. According to seasonal dynamics, 95% in spring, 5.0% in summer, 10.5% in autumn, 55.0% in winter, the highest damage is observed in spring and winter, and the minimum damage is observed in summer.

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